

building-integrated user-
empowered flexibility trading

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Executive Summary

The objective of this document is to present the preparation and setup of the technical infrastructure required to support the BlueBird reference architecture. It provides a detailed overview of the enabling technologies, the overall IT architecture, the implementation of the BlueBird data model, and the procedures for preparing and managing data.

The architecture has been defined with a strong emphasis on flexibility and adaptability, ensuring that it can integrate seamlessly with the existing IT environments of project partners. Many partners already operate IT architectures to support their current services; therefore, the BlueBird architecture has been designed to complement these infrastructures rather than replace them. This approach minimises disruption and maximises reusability of existing systems.

By following this strategy, the project ensures that the deployment of BlueBird services is not only feasible during the project lifetime but also sustainable in the long term. Once the project concludes, partners will be able to continue providing and scaling the developed services within their own infrastructures, maintaining the value created and supporting ongoing innovation in energy management and flexibility services.

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Acronyms and Definitions

Acronym	Definition
AI	Artificial Intelligence
BC	Business Case
BEMS	Building Energy Management Systems
CA	Consortium Agreement
CC	Creative Commons
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DPO	Data Protection Officer
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
EUPL	European Union Public License
EV	Electric Vehicle
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
HVAC	Heating, Ventilating and Air Conditioning
ICT	Information & Communication Technologies
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
M	Month
MS	Milestones
PV	Photovoltaic
UBFlex	Universal Building Flexibility Interface
WP	Work Package

I. INTRODUCTION

This deliverable provides a detailed description of the BlueBird big data reference architecture, offering a comprehensive overview of the enabling technologies, the overall IT architecture, the implementation of the BlueBird data model, and the procedures for data preparation and management.

As one of the main deliverables of Work Package 6 (WP6), this document outlines the technical specifications and design principles of the architecture. It describes the elementary BlueBird components, software units with clearly defined purposes such as retrieving data, transforming data, analysing data, and coordinating data flows. It also outlines the architectural options available for organising and deploying these components.

A key finding from the project is that, to meet the requirements of the pilot sites, the BlueBird architecture cannot rely solely on a cloud-based system. Instead, the proposed solution has been designed to be modular and flexible, offering a variety of deployment choices for BlueBird components. This proposed solution is achieved through a “pick-and-choose” approach, in which end users can select and deploy only the components they need. Complementary architectural guidelines describe state-of-the-art methods for organising and managing interactions among these components.

The architecture has been developed with a strong emphasis on flexibility and adaptability, ensuring smooth integration with the existing IT infrastructures of project partners. Many partners already operate established IT systems to deliver their services, and the BlueBird architecture is therefore designed to complement and extend these systems rather than replace them. This approach minimises disruption while maximising the reuse of existing infrastructures and resources.

This strategy ensures that the deployment of BlueBird services is not only feasible during the project lifetime but also sustainable in the long term and replicable abroad. Once the project concludes, partners will be able to maintain and scale the developed services within their own infrastructures, preserving the value created and supporting ongoing innovation in energy management and flexibility solutions.

II. TECHNICAL APPROACH

This chapter outlines the key technical architecture decisions made for the BlueBird framework, independently of the internal design of individual BlueBird components. These decisions stem from a comparative evaluation of practical technical options, informed by the prior experience and technical expertise of the participating project partners.

The architecture choices were guided by several core objectives:

- **Modularity and Reusability:** To ensure the BlueBird framework is composed of modular, reusable components that can be easily deployed across a variety of anticipated IT environments.
- **Integration Flexibility:** To support multiple integration strategies for BlueBird components, reflecting the diverse methodologies and use cases observed among project stakeholders.

Based on an analysis of current data collection and processing practices among the partners, three primary usage patterns for the software components produced by the BlueBird project have been identified:

1. **Command Line Interface Usage:** BlueBird components can be executed from the command line, a common approach in data engineering for assembling data processing pipelines. In this setup, tools are interconnected through the exchange of data files, with each component configured using command-line options and producing or consuming files as needed.
2. **Web Service API Access:** Components can be exposed as online services via RESTful web APIs. This is a widely adopted method, particularly in cases where computationally intensive processing is required—processing that may not be feasible to perform on end-users' local systems.
3. **Event Stream Messaging Integration:** Components can also operate as nodes within an event stream messaging architecture. This is the preferred approach for big data use cases involving the real-time processing of streaming events. Unlike traditional message queuing (MQ) systems, event stream messaging offers better scalability and performance for live data ingestion and analytics.

To support these three interaction paradigms, each BlueBird component should be available in one or more of the following formats:

- **Command Line Interface Tool:** A standalone executable or script that can be configured via command-line options, consumes and/or produces data files, and is suitable for scripting or batch processing workflows.
- **Web API Service:** A service exposing a REST API, allowing remote access and integration over HTTP protocols. This enables seamless interoperability with other software systems or user interfaces.
- **Kafka-Compatible Messaging Node:** A component designed to interface with an event streaming platform. In the context of BlueBird, Apache Kafka has been selected as the standard event stream messaging system for the Reference Architecture Framework. Components must be implemented as Kafka producers (publishing data to topics) and/or consumers (subscribing to topics) to ensure compatibility.

Importantly, these distribution formats are language-agnostic—meaning they do not constrain the choice of programming language used to build end-user applications or services that consume BlueBird components. This ensures maximum flexibility and broad adoption potential across various technical ecosystems.

II.1. Vision

One of the most common challenges when deploying software in existing IT environments is ensuring compatibility with the host operating system (OS), as well as with the pre-installed services and software libraries. A typical scenario involves an application that depends on a specific version of a library or tool. If a different version of that dependency is already installed on the target system, a conflict can arise. Installing the application without updating the dependency may result in a failure to run, while updating the dependency could disrupt or break other parts of the system that rely on the existing version. This situation is widely recognised in the software development community as “dependency hell.”

To mitigate this problem, modern software development has widely adopted containerisation technologies, most notably Docker. Containerisation offers a practical solution by enabling applications to run in isolated environments that include all necessary dependencies, thereby avoiding conflicts with those installed on the host system.

Unlike traditional virtualisation, which involves running a full guest OS atop a host OS, containerisation operates with minimal overhead. Containers share the host OS kernel while maintaining complete separation of their file systems, dependencies, and execution environments. Therefore, compared to virtualisation, containerisation makes applications lightweight, efficient, and highly portable.

The core artifact used in Docker-based deployments is the Docker image. A Docker image can be thought of as a self-contained snapshot of the application environment. It includes the application code along with all its required libraries, runtime, and system tools. Once built, a Docker image can be instantiated as a container, which runs independently of the host system’s installed software.

Docker images are flexible in that they can package both long-running services (such as servers or APIs) and one-off processes (such as command-line tools that execute a task and exit). This flexibility makes container technology particularly well-suited for supporting the three distribution models discussed earlier in this document:

- Command Line Interface tools
- Web service APIs
- Event stream messaging components

To facilitate support for these multiple forms of component deployment, one effective strategy is to design the core business logic as a shared library. Various lightweight wrappers would then utilise this library, each tailored to a specific deployment form: one as a Command-Line Interface, another as a REST API, and another as a Kafka-compatible event processing component. This approach promotes code reuse, simplifies testing, and ensures consistent behaviour across deployment models.

It is worth noting that not all teams need to implement every variant of each component. Development teams are free to select the technologies and deployment strategies that best align with the needs, constraints, and priorities of their respective pilot implementations. For example, some Business Cases operate critical infrastructure, so to ensure security managers inspect them, they will receive the code directly. Then they will be in charge of installing the services as it fits better in their IT structure. Moreover, as they deploy their solutions, which could be deployed on a central server connected to their appliances or decentralised, using edge computing, each pilot is responsible for ensuring security and privacy on its own side. For all deployments, we encourage the use of secure technologies for information transfer (e.g., HTTPS, MQTT over SSL) between components, ensuring that the data remains safe and private.

Figure 1. BlueBird components interface code, distribution mechanisms and deployment

Figure 1 illustrates the technical strategy adopted by the BlueBird project to develop, package, and distribute its service components across all consortium partners. The objective is to ensure efficient collaboration, interoperability, and smooth deployment of BlueBird solutions in various environments. The process can be broken down into the following key steps, enumerated as in Figure 1:

1. **Service software development:** For each specific service offered by the BlueBird framework—such as data ingestion, data harmonisation, data analysis, or data quality improvement—a dedicated software module must be developed. These service modules encapsulate the core business logic, value-added mechanisms, and domain-specific features created by BlueBird developers. In some cases, services are tailored to particular business cases. These modules typically rely on specialised technologies and libraries best suited to their task, such as Python + Pandas for data manipulation and R + ggplot2 for statistical analysis and visualisation. This flexibility allows developers to implement efficient, context-appropriate solutions.
2. **Wrapping services with interface implementations:** Once a service’s core logic is implemented, it can be wrapped with various interfaces to support different usage and deployment models. The goal is to make the services accessible in a way that best fits the intended operational environment. The three main interface options, as mentioned previously, are:
 - Command Line Interface for local execution and scripting scenarios.
 - Web Service with REST API for integration into web-based systems and cloud services.
 - Event Stream Messaging Interface for integration into real-time data processing pipelines.

For event-driven architectures, Apache Kafka has been selected as the standard streaming platform within the BlueBird reference framework.

3. **Containerisation for deployment:** To simplify deployment across diverse infrastructure setups, whether on cloud platforms or on-premises systems, all wrapped components should be containerised using Docker. Packaging components as Docker images ensures:
 - Consistent runtime environments.
 - Isolation from host system dependencies.

- Reduced configuration effort during deployment: This step is critical to achieving frictionless deployment and avoiding environment-specific issues.
4. **Centralised image registry for component distribution:** All Dockerised components must be published to a centralised BlueBird Image Registry. This registry serves as a shared repository where consortium partners can:
 - Discover available services.
 - Access the correct deployment versions.
 - Retrieve assets as needed based on their business requirements and infrastructure constraints.
 5. **Support for multiple component versions and interface options:** Each service may be made available in one or more interface formats, depending on the needs of different services and business cases. The component registry could store:
 - The core service logic (source code).
 - Multiple “wrapped” versions of the same service, each targeting a specific interaction method.
 - Corresponding Docker images, ready for deployment: This modular approach allows partners to select and use the most appropriate version of each component for their specific context.
 6. **Deployment and integration by partners:** Finally, each project partner is responsible for implementing real-world use cases. For this reason, they can:
 - Browse the registry.
 - Retrieve the appropriate component versions.
 - Deploy and integrate them into their local infrastructure: This can be done either by using the BlueBird Reference Big Data Architecture or by incorporating the components into custom architectures tailored to their operational needs.

II.2. Distribution mechanism

A practical and efficient method for distributing Docker images created by contributors is to host them on a container registry. This approach simplifies access and deployment for end users, enabling seamless sharing and reuse of software components across different environments.

By linking the container registry with the source code repository used for version control, each component’s development and deployment resources are centralised in a single location. This integrated setup ensures that the latest version of the component—along with its complete runtime environment—is readily accessible from the same platform where the code is maintained.

Once an image has been published to the registry, deploying the component is straightforward. Users only need to ensure their local system is configured to access the registry (e.g., by logging in or adding the appropriate registry URL). After that, the component can be launched using the standard Docker command:

```
docker run <registry-url>/<image-name>:<tag>
```

This method enables users to:

- Pull and execute the latest version of a component with minimal setup.
- Avoid manual installation of dependencies or environment configuration.
- Ensure consistency across deployments, regardless of the host system.

In summary, using a container registry as the central distribution hub for Docker images promotes ease of use, scalability, and reliability in deploying BlueBird components across the consortium and beyond.

II.3. General guidelines for components

As previously outlined, BlueBird components are designed to be accessible through multiple interfaces, namely, the command line interface, web services exposing REST APIs, and Kafka-compatible event stream messaging systems. This multi-interface approach ensures flexibility and adaptability to a wide variety of deployment scenarios.

To support seamless integration and interoperability, all components must follow consistent data exchange standards and interface conventions. This standardisation ensures that consuming systems—be they other software modules, developers, or end-users—are not required to accommodate varying, component-specific formats or protocols. By adhering to unified standards, the BlueBird framework provides a professional, coherent, and industrial-grade interface across all components, thereby enhancing usability and promoting scalability.

II.3.1. Command line interface integration guidelines

Command line interface¹ tools should adopt standardised practices to ensure consistency and ease of use:

- **Use positional arguments** to specify datasets, both input and output.
- **Use options** (flags or named parameters) for configuring process parameters. These options should provide sensible default values to simplify usage for common scenarios.

Example usage:

```
$ bluebird-tool /path/to/input1 /path/to/input2 /path/to/output \  
--option1 foo --option2 bar
```

If the tool processes a single dataset, support for standard input (*stdin*) and standard output (*stdout*) should be implemented. This standard implementation enables users to construct data processing pipelines without needing intermediate files, enhancing both speed and efficiency.

If using *stdin/stdout*, make sure progress or log messages are directed to *stderr* to avoid contaminating data streams.

Command line interface tools should adhere to standard Unix conventions:

- Exit code *0* for success.
- Non-zero exit codes for various failure scenarios (e.g., invalid arguments, missing files).
- Implement *-h/--help* to display usage information and optionally include links to detailed documentation.
- Implement *--version* to output the component's version number.

This approach enhances composability, scriptability, and overall developer experience.

If only one input dataset is needed, the tool should support piping from *stdin*, allowing it to be part of a larger data-processing chain. In such cases, output should be sent to *stdout*. Use of "-" (a dash) as a placeholder for *stdin/stdout* is optional but recommended for compatibility.

¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Command-line_interface

II.3.2. Web service integration guidelines

Web-based components should follow RESTful API design principles to enable standardised and intuitive usage:

- HTTP POST must be used for operations that require complex inputs, especially when datasets are involved. The request body should use *multipart/form-data* encoding².
- If no datasets are included, *application/x-www-form-urlencoded*³ encoding may be used. However, this is discouraged due to increased complexity without a significant performance gain.
- If the service returns a dataset, it must be included in the HTTP response body, with the appropriate Content-Type header⁴ accurately reflecting the data type.
- HTTP status codes must reflect the outcome:
 - 200: OK for successful processing.
 - 400: Bad Request for malformed requests.
 - 422: Unprocessable Entity for domain-specific errors due to invalid input.
 - 500 Internal Server Error for unexpected failures.
- Self-Documentation Endpoints:
 - Implement GET */help* to return usage information.
 - Implement GET */version* to return the service version in plain text.

Clear documentation of all input parameters, output formats, and potential response headers is essential for fostering user confidence and enabling rapid integration.

II.3.3. Event stream messaging system (Kafka) integration guidelines

Before integrating Kafka⁵ into any system or service architecture, it is essential to understand the fundamental concepts that make up Kafka's ecosystem. Kafka is a high-performance, distributed streaming platform that enables real-time data processing through decoupled and scalable components. The following are its core building blocks:

- **Producer:** an application or service responsible for publishing data to Kafka topics. In Kafka, each unit of data sent by a producer is called a record. This record may include a key, a value, a timestamp, and optional headers. Kafka treats records as opaque byte arrays, meaning it does not impose any restrictions on the data format — it could be text, binary, JSON, Avro, Protobuf, or any other encoding. This flexibility allows producers to adapt to a variety of use cases and domains.
- **Consumer:** an application that subscribes to Kafka topics and processes the records. It polls Kafka continuously for new records and typically commits the offset (the position within the partition) after processing, which ensures reliable delivery. Kafka's consumer API enables features like rebalancing within consumer groups and manual or automatic offset management. This management enables the building of resilient and scalable consumption logic tailored to specific application needs.

² <https://developer.mozilla.org/en-US/docs/Web/HTTP/Methods/POST>

³ <https://developer.mozilla.org/en-US/docs/Web/HTTP/Methods/POST>

⁴ <https://developer.mozilla.org/en-US/docs/Web/HTTP/Headers/Content-Type>

⁵ <https://kafka.apache.org/>

- **Broker:** a Kafka server that stores topic data and serves client requests from both producers and consumers. Each broker handles data persistence, partition replication, and client coordination. Kafka brokers are designed to work together as part of a cluster, ensuring scalability and fault tolerance. A single Kafka cluster may consist of multiple brokers that jointly manage topic partitions and balance the workload.
- **Connectors:** specialised Kafka components used to integrate Kafka with external data systems. Kafka provides the Kafka Connect framework, which simplifies the task of importing and exporting data by offering ready-to-use source connectors (which pull data into Kafka from external systems) and sink connectors (which push Kafka data into external systems).
- **Cluster:** Kafka cluster is a distributed system made up of multiple brokers working together. Each broker is responsible for a subset of topic partitions and coordinates with other brokers to ensure data replication and consistency. Clustering enables Kafka to scale horizontally by adding more brokers to accommodate higher volumes of data and throughput. Additionally, Kafka clusters support automatic failover and partition leadership election to maintain service availability.

Figure 2. Kafka cluster representation⁶

- **Topic:** a named logical channel to which producers write records and from which consumers read. Topics can be configured for retention policies, such as keeping records for a fixed duration or until a certain size threshold is reached. Kafka topics are immutable — once data is written, it is never changed — making them suitable for event logging, audit trails, and temporal analytics.
- **Partition:** each topic is divided into one or more partitions, which are the basic units of parallelism in Kafka. A partition is an ordered sequence of records, and Kafka guarantees that records are written and read in order within a partition. Distributing partitions across brokers enables Kafka to scale out processing across multiple machines. Producers can control which partition a message goes to using partitioning strategies like round-robin, key-based hashing, or custom logic.
- **Offset:** a unique identifier for a record within a partition. Offsets are incremental and immutable: the first record has an offset of 0, the second has 1, and so on. Consumers use offsets to track their position in a partition and can choose to commit them manually or automatically. Kafka allows seeking to a specific offset, making it possible to replay data or resume from a particular point in case of failure.

Because offsets are scoped per partition, a record is uniquely identified by its topic name, partition number, and offset. This design supports precise message tracking and reliable delivery semantics.

⁶ <https://kafka.apache.org/0100/documentation.html>

- **Consumer Group:** a logical grouping of one or more consumers working together to consume records from a topic. Kafka ensures that each partition in a topic is assigned to only one consumer within a group, allowing for parallel processing without duplication. When a new consumer joins or leaves the group, Kafka automatically rebalances the partitions among the available consumers. This model supports scalability and resilience in data processing pipelines.

If the number of consumers exceeds the number of partitions, some consumers will remain idle (useful as failover backups). If the number of consumers is fewer than the number of partitions, each consumer will handle multiple partitions.

II.4. BlueBird components' versatile integration options

As outlined in the preceding chapters, BlueBird components can be distributed using three main integration mechanisms: command line interface, web services, and event stream messaging systems (e.g., Kafka). Each of these mechanisms involves different technical approaches for passing input data to the components and receiving output from them.

Once a component is containerised (e.g., packaged into a Docker image), various options become available for handling its inputs and outputs. These options vary depending on the selected distribution method and the interaction model.

The following table summarises the possible input/output methods that can be used with Dockerised BlueBird components, categorised by integration type:

Table 1. Input/output methods that can be used with Dockerised BlueBird components

Distribution Mechanism	Input Method	Output Method	Ref.
Command line interface	Environment variables pointing to shared storage locations	Output references written to shared storage locations	1
	Command line arguments (e.g., paths, flags, parameters)	CLI execution returns status or stores output externally	2
	File stream via STDIN	File stream via STDOUT	3
	Mounted volume/folder containing input files	Mounted volume/folder for output files	4
Web Service	API request with parameters and data (usually via HTTP POST)	API response containing the result or a reference to the output	5
Event Stream Messaging	Input messages from a message queue (e.g., Kafka topic)	Output messages sent to a target queue/topic	6

Each mechanism brings different strengths and trade-offs in terms of performance, scalability, data throughput, and ease of integration. Here's a brief explanation of each row in the table:

1. **Environment variables pointing to shared storage locations:** When a Dockerised component is executed via the command line interpreter, environment variables can be used to pass configuration data, such as credentials or connection strings, to shared storage systems (e.g., databases, cloud storage). These shared systems act as input and output repositories, allowing components to access large datasets without requiring the data to be passed directly via the

command line. Therefore, they are used to pass configuration or data references to the container at runtime, often pointing to shared file systems or cloud storage buckets.

2. **Command line arguments:** components can receive input data via traditional command line parameters. These arguments typically specify file paths, numeric values, flags, or string values required by the component for processing. Output can be generated based on the execution context, typically written to specified locations.
3. **File stream via *stdin*:** using standard Unix-like I/O streams, Dockerised components can be configured to read input data from *stdin* and write output to *stdout*. This standardization enables easy chaining of multiple command-line interface tools using pipes and minimizes disk I/O by avoiding intermediate file writes. It is particularly useful for lightweight or real-time data processing scenarios.
4. **Mounted volume/folder containing input files:** Docker allows mounting host directories into the container's file system. Input data can be placed in a mounted folder that the component reads from, and output results can be saved in a designated output folder. This method is well-suited for handling large files or batch processing jobs.
5. **Web Service API request with parameters and data:** if the component exposes a web service interface, data can be sent via HTTP methods such as *POST*, *GET*, or *PUT*. The input typically includes parameters, file uploads, or metadata in a structured format like JSON or multipart/form-data. The output is returned in the HTTP response, which can include result data, download links, or processing summaries.
6. **Event stream messaging input messages from a message queue:** when the component is integrated with an event-driven architecture, input data is received through messages (records) published to a stream, such as a Kafka topic. The component processes each message and publishes the result to another topic or queue. This approach supports high-throughput, asynchronous data workflows.

These options provide a flexible framework for deploying BlueBird components in diverse environments while supporting automation, pipeline chaining, and interoperability across different systems.

III. BLUEBIRD BIG DATA REFERENCE ARCHITECTURE FRAMEWORK

III.1. Big data key concepts

III.1.1. Definition

Big Data refers to a complex ecosystem of concepts, technologies, architectures, and frameworks that work together toward a common goal: efficiently managing and extracting value from vast amounts of data. Given the scale, diversity, and rapid generation of data in today's digital world, traditional data management approaches have become insufficient.

To define and understand Big Data more effectively, experts⁷ have adopted a model based on five key characteristics commonly referred to as the 5 Vs of Big Data. While additional "V" terms have been proposed over time (some lists now include up to 10), the foundational 5 Vs remain the most widely recognised.

Figure 3. 5 Vs of Big Data

1. Volume – The Scale of Data

Volume refers to the sheer quantity of data being generated and stored. Today, organisations accumulate data from a multitude of sources: databases, enterprise applications, IoT sensors, mobile devices, websites, and user-generated content such as emails, documents, images, videos, and social media posts.

This explosion of data has outpaced traditional storage and processing technologies. Organisations are now dealing with terabytes to petabytes of structured and unstructured data. Managing this scale demands scalable storage solutions (e.g., cloud platforms, distributed file systems) and advanced processing frameworks such as Hadoop and Spark.

Without modern infrastructure, analysing such massive volumes of data becomes impractical or even impossible.

2. Velocity – The Speed of Data Flow

Velocity defines the rate at which data is created, collected, and analysed. In the modern digital landscape, data flows continuously and rapidly from various sources—social networks, financial markets, mobile apps, IoT devices, and more.

⁷ <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1877050915006973>

This streaming data must be captured and processed in near real-time to derive timely insights and enable responsive decision-making. Delays in data processing can lead to missed opportunities or ineffective actions.

Technologies like Apache Kafka, Apache Flink, and real-time analytics platforms allow businesses to ingest and analyse data as it is generated, ensuring decisions are based on the most current information.

3. Value – Extracting Business Insights

Of all the Vs, Value is arguably the most important. Not all data is inherently useful—its real power lies in the ability to extract actionable insights that influence business outcomes.

Organisations must move beyond simply collecting and storing data. Value is realised through data analytics, which helps uncover trends, patterns, and predictions that guide strategic decisions, optimise operations, and create competitive advantage.

However, deriving value involves balancing cost and return. It's essential to assess:

- What resources are needed to store, process, and analyse the data?
- What measurable benefits (e.g., improved customer retention, revenue growth) can be gained?

A cost-benefit analysis can help determine whether investing in Big Data analytics will deliver a meaningful return on investment.

4. Veracity – Ensuring Data Quality

Veracity refers to the accuracy, reliability, and trustworthiness of data. With data flowing in from countless sources—often inconsistently formatted or incomplete—questions naturally arise:

- Can this data be trusted?
- Is it accurate and up-to-date?
- Should decisions be made based on it?

Poor data quality can lead to flawed insights and misguided strategies. That's why it's critical to:

- Validate data during ingestion
- Use data cleansing and enrichment tools
- Apply governance policies to ensure integrity

Big Data tools often include features to manage data quality, duplication, noise, and anomalies, helping ensure that decisions are based on sound information.

5. Variety – Handling Diverse Data Types

Big Data isn't just big in size or speed—it's also diverse in form. Data comes in a wide range of types and formats, typically classified into three categories:

- **Structured data:** Clearly defined format and schema (e.g., relational databases, spreadsheets, timeseries databases)
- **Semi-structured data:** Partial organisation, often tagged but not fully structured (e.g., XML, JSON, log files)
- **Unstructured data:** No predefined format (e.g., emails, social media posts, videos, audio files)

An estimated 80% of the world's data is unstructured, and traditional systems struggle to process it effectively. Big Data platforms are designed to ingest, process, and analyse all forms of data from internal systems and external channels—such as websites, mobile apps, and cloud services.

Understanding and managing this variety is crucial for building a 360-degree view of the business and customer behavior.

III.1.2. Layers

To fully realise the potential promised by the 5 Vs of Big Data, modern Big Data architectures are designed using a layered approach. Each layer handles a specific set of responsibilities, contributing to a scalable, efficient, and insightful data ecosystem.

Figure 4. Big Data Architecture Layers

1.- Data Source Layer

This is the foundational layer, where data is initially generated and collected. Big Data systems must handle an extensive variety of data sources, which may include:

- **Internal systems:** enterprise databases, ERP systems, IoT devices, log files.
- **External feeds:** APIs, open data, web scraping, third-party data vendors.
- **Streaming sources:** social media platforms, user clickstreams, network sensors, mobile apps.

Data can arrive through both:

- Push mechanisms (data producers actively send data),
- Pull mechanisms (the system periodically fetches data).

Moreover, the data may be:

- Structured (e.g., relational databases),
- Unstructured (e.g., images, video, free-text documents).

The data is split into two flows:

- Real-time/streaming data is immediately processed by the processing layer.
- Historical/batch data is stored in the data lake within the storage layer for future analysis.

2.- Data Storage Layer

All incoming raw data, regardless of its format, is persistently stored in this layer. This is commonly done in systems optimised for scalability and schema flexibility, such as Hadoop Distributed File System (HDFS) or NoSQL databases like MongoDB, Cassandra, or Amazon DynamoDB. The storage approach is often schema-on-read, meaning that a Structure is applied only when the data is later read and analysed. Such a storage repository is usually referred to as a data lake. The metaphor suggests that all types of data sources pour

data into a single, large pool, just like rivers flowing into a lake. To improve discoverability and usability, metadata, labels, and indexes are attached to the raw data, either manually or automatically using data cataloguing tools.

3.- Data Processing and Analysis Layer

In this layer, raw data from the data lake is transformed, filtered, enriched, and analysed to extract meaningful information. Key processes include:

- **Data cleaning:** handling missing, inconsistent, or incorrect data
- **Data transformation:** reformatting and structuring data into usable formats
- **Aggregation and correlation:** combining data from different sources to build context

The concept of “lakeshore” is introduced to define a repository containing structured, mapped and organised data, derived from the raw data contained in the data lake. The lakeshore contains structured, pre-processed, and organised datasets. It is optimised for machine learning (ML), artificial intelligence (AI), business intelligence, and analytics workloads.

4.- Data Output Layer

This layer is responsible for delivering insights to end-users, applications, or systems that will act upon the analysis. Output can take multiple forms:

- Reports and dashboards using tools like Tableau, Power BI, and Grafana
- APIs providing live metrics to external services
- Alerts and notifications based on predefined thresholds or anomalies
- Data exports to other business applications or automated workflows

The primary goal of this layer is to support decision-making by providing timely, relevant, and interpretable results. This goal may involve showcasing improvements to key performance indicators (KPIs), forecasting future trends, or identifying operational inefficiencies. Some output applications may require real-time data consumption, necessitating low-latency access to the latest results via NoSQL databases or in-memory data grids.

III.1.3. Lambda and Kappa Architecture

To meet the complex demands of Big Data systems, particularly those involving real-time processing and long-term storage, architectural patterns have been developed to strike a balance between scalability, performance, and maintainability. Two of the most prominent reference architectures for managing large-scale data processing are the Lambda Architecture and the Kappa Architecture.

Lambda Architecture

Initially proposed by Nathan Marz, the Lambda Architecture is one of the earliest and most influential models for Big Data architecture. It is designed to handle massive volumes of data by dividing the data processing pipeline into three main layers, each with a distinct responsibility:

1. **Batch Layer:** This layer ingests all incoming raw data and stores it permanently in a distributed storage system (such as HDFS or S3). It performs pre-computation on this data, often via MapReduce or Spark, to generate views (aggregated or summarised data), which are periodically updated and delivered to the Serving Layer.
2. **Speed Layer:** While the batch layer provides accuracy, it is not suitable for real-time use cases. The speed layer addresses this by processing data as it arrives (using technologies like Apache Storm, Flink, or Kafka Streams). It provides low-latency, real-time views based on the most recent data that the batch system hasn't yet processed.

3. **Serving Layer:** This layer merges the outputs of the batch and speed layers to provide comprehensive, up-to-date results to the end users or applications. Since the Serving Layer draws from two different sources, it has a “strabismic” or dual vision, balancing the accuracy of the batch layer with the timeliness of the speed layer.

Figure 5. Lambda Architecture representation for the BlueBird project

Lambda Architecture is particularly effective in scenarios requiring both historical and real-time analysis, such as fraud detection, recommendation engines, and IoT applications.

Kappa Architecture

As Big Data technologies evolved, practitioners began to recognise the complexity and operational overhead of maintaining two separate processing pipelines (batch and speed). In response, Jay Kreps proposed the Kappa Architecture, which aims to simplify data processing by relying on a single, unified streaming layer.

Key features of Kappa Architecture include:

- **Single Processing Pipeline:** Unlike Lambda, there is no separate batch system. All data is processed as a stream, including historical reprocessing. If you need to reprocess data (e.g., due to updated logic or code), you simply replay the original data stream from a persistent log (such as Apache Kafka).
- **Reprocessing Capabilities:** Since all data is stored in a replayable format, new logic or models can be applied to the existing data stream by running them through the same stream processing engine. The results are then used to update views or services.
- **Simplicity in Maintenance:** One of the primary advantages is that there is only one codebase and one execution model to maintain, thereby reducing complexity and potential inconsistencies.

Figure 6. Kappa Architecture

Kappa Architecture is ideal for systems where real-time analytics are prioritised and batch processing is not a hard requirement, or where infrastructure simplicity and agility are more critical than computational optimisation.

When to Use Which?

Lambda Architecture is best suited for:

- Applications requiring high accuracy through comprehensive historical analysis.
- Use cases involving complex computations or machine learning models that are expensive and require optimisation.
- Scenarios where batch results significantly differ from real-time outputs and both are required.

Kappa Architecture is more appropriate when:

- You want a simpler, easier-to-maintain architecture.
- The system is primarily streaming-oriented.
- Batch reprocessing can be handled through stream replay mechanisms.
- You want to maintain a single processing engine and logic base.

Both architectures are suitable for deploying the BlueBird services. Depending on the specific service, one architecture may be better suited to the requirements than the other; however, both should be able to accommodate the BlueBird services effectively.

Table 2. Lambda Architecture and Kappa Architecture comparison

Feature / Aspect	Lambda Architecture	Kappa Architecture
Purpose	Unified batch + stream data processing	Simplified stream-only data processing
Data Flow	Dual path: batch layer (for completeness) + speed layer (for real-time)	Single path: all data is treated as a real-time stream
Complexity	High: requires maintaining two codebases (batch and stream processing logic)	Lower: single codebase for both real-time and reprocessing
Data Reprocessing	Done in the batch layer by re-running historical jobs	Done by replaying the data stream through the same engine
Use Case Fit	Best when batch and stream analytics are both needed and offer complementary results	Ideal when stream processing alone can meet all analytical requirements
Fault Tolerance	Higher resilience through batch layer	Dependent on stream replay capabilities and durability of the messaging system
Serving Layer	Pre-computes and stores batch views for access	Real-time layer serves queries directly from stream-processed data
Latency	Higher (due to batch processing delays)	Lower (stream-only = near real-time analytics)
Code Maintenance	More challenging (2 separate pipelines to manage)	Easier (one unified stream pipeline)
System Resources	Requires more resources due to dual systems	More efficient in terms of compute and maintenance
Examples of Use	Fraud detection, recommendation systems needing both real-time and complete history	Real-time dashboards, IoT analytics, log/event processing with no batch component
Data Replay Requirement	Not required (batch system handles historical data)	Mandatory (must support full or partial stream reprocessing)
Storage	Data stored both in batch systems (e.g., Hadoop) and stream systems (e.g., Kafka)	Data stored primarily in the stream processing system

III.2. BlueBird reference architecture framework description

III.2.1. The concept of harmonised data

Techniques for collecting and analysing building energy data have advanced significantly in recent years, propelled by rapid technological innovation and increasing global emphasis on energy efficiency and sustainability. These advancements have improved the precision, timeliness, and availability of data, enabling new opportunities to monitor, evaluate, and optimise energy performance across the built environment. However, despite the wealth of available data, one of the most pressing obstacles remains: the lack of standardisation and harmonisation in how energy data is defined, structured, and exchanged across various systems, platforms, and applications. Diverse data formats, terminologies, and siloed databases often prevent seamless integration and practical analysis, limiting the potential of data-driven strategies in building energy management.

The BlueBird project is designed to address this critical challenge head-on. At its core, the project aims to develop an open-source Big Data Reference Architecture alongside a suite of interoperable BlueBird services. These components are built to support a wide range of real-world use cases spanning the entire building lifecycle, from design and construction to operation, renovation, and end-of-life decision-making. A fundamental pillar of the BlueBird approach is the harmonisation of data semantics across heterogeneous systems. To achieve this, the project harnesses the capabilities of semantic technologies, with a strong focus on the use of ontologies. Ontologies provide a machine-readable, structured framework for representing the meaning of data and the relationships between different concepts. They serve as a shared vocabulary that promotes interoperability, consistency, and semantic alignment across diverse sources and tools. Through this approach, BlueBird enables automated data exchange, integration, and interpretation across platforms that were traditionally isolated from one another, such as Building Management Systems (BMS), IoT-based monitoring solutions, Building Information Modelling (BIM), and energy auditing software.

A key principle in the development of the BlueBird semantic model is the reuse and alignment of existing ontologies, such as the BIGG ontology, which leverages several existing ontologies to integrate a wide variety of data and manage building data for energy analysis purposes. By building upon these existing resources rather than creating new ones from scratch, the project ensures semantic consistency, avoids duplication of effort, and strengthens interoperability with broader ecosystems. This strategy lays a robust foundation for integrating heterogeneous datasets while preserving their original context and meaning. The resulting unified data model not only facilitates advanced analytics and AI-driven insights but also supports scalability, replicability, and long-term sustainability of digital solutions in the building sector.

III.2.2. Reference architecture framework overview

The BlueBird project introduces a detailed reference architecture framework to enable efficient, accurate, and standardised handling of building-related data. The core idea is to apply data harmonisation to support data-driven applications throughout the building life cycle. The BlueBird reference architecture framework is composed of a modular pipeline of components that can be flexibly orchestrated, typically through a message broker for real-time data exchange. Figure 7 illustrates this architecture, with numbered components referenced throughout this report.

Figure 7. BlueBird reference architecture framework overview

The ingestion modules are software components that retrieve data from diverse sources, including IoT sensors, Building Management Systems, and third-party platforms. Standard protocols such as HTTP and MQTT are used to ensure robust and interoperable data acquisition.

The ingested data is either stored in data lakes for batch processing or pushed to the next module using an event-driven message bus, such as Apache Kafka. This process ensures low-latency delivery to downstream processes.

At the heart of the architecture is the harmonisation module, which converts incoming data into the BlueBird data model using a mapping file. This model is built on ontologies to ensure semantic consistency and interoperability. Data harmonisation improves data quality, facilitates integration across systems, and supports advanced analytics. It ensures that data is semantically aligned, enabling meaningful insights into energy consumption and performance.

Harmonised data is fed into the service modules, which employ machine learning and AI techniques to generate insights, forecasts, and optimisation recommendations. Dashboards and external systems use the outputs to visualise data and control building systems. This final step transforms harmonised insights back into formats compatible with end-user applications.

Further sections in this document will provide in-depth technical specifications and integration guidelines for each reference architecture framework component.

III.2.3. Reference architecture framework connectivity: Message Broker

Regardless of the chosen Big Data reference architecture, whether it follows the Lambda or Kappa paradigm, one critical component is universally indispensable: the message broker. This software module acts as a message-oriented middleware, serving as a central communication layer that facilitates the seamless flow of data between various microservices and components.

In essence, a message broker functions as an intermediary agent that decouples services, enabling them to interact asynchronously and efficiently. Especially in microservices-based architectures, where modularity, scalability, and loose coupling are key design principles, the message broker plays a pivotal role by offering a wide range of features that support robust, flexible, and real-time data processing.

A modern message broker offers several core capabilities:

- **Topic-Based Routing with Publish/Subscribe Pattern:** Enables services to publish messages to specific topics and allows subscribers to listen only to the topics they are interested in, reducing unnecessary data processing.
- **Multi-Target Message Routing:** Supports forwarding messages to one or multiple microservices simultaneously, facilitating parallel and distributed data processing.
- **Message Queuing:** Buffers messages for batch processing, ensuring that data is not lost even when the receiving service is temporarily unavailable.
- **Loose Coupling Between Services:** Promotes architectural flexibility by decoupling message producers from consumers, allowing services to evolve independently.
- **Reliable Delivery with Storage and Buffering:** Temporarily stores messages to guarantee delivery, even in the event of service interruptions or failures.
- **Partitioning and Load Balancing:** Distributes messages across different partitions or nodes to optimise throughput and ensure high availability.
- **Event-Driven Choreography:** Enables services to interact and coordinate their actions through events rather than direct calls, supporting a more dynamic and scalable system architecture.

To effectively utilise a message broker, we can identify three primary service archetypes, as illustrated in Figure 8:

Figure 8. Three fundamental service archetypes for a Big Data architecture

Producer: A producer is a service that generates and publishes messages to specific topics on the message broker. For instance, a service that collects data from IoT devices and sends it to a designated topic acts as a producer. In many architectures, this is referred to as an ingestor, whose primary role is to introduce new data into the system.

Processor: A processor consumes messages from one topic, performs computations, transformations, or enrichments, and then publishes the result to another topic. This type of service is fundamental for data harmonisation, such as transforming messages from proprietary formats into a standardised format like the BlueBird data model. Processors act as intermediaries that prepare data for advanced analytics and machine learning workflows.

Consumer: A consumer subscribes to one or more topics to retrieve and process messages. Consumers can serve various purposes, such as storing messages in databases, invoking external services, generating logs, or feeding visualisation dashboards. These are often referred to as adapters, as they adapt the processed data for final use or integration with other systems (e.g., Building Management Systems).

Together, these three service archetypes form the backbone of a scalable, modular, and resilient event-driven data architecture, ensuring that data flows are efficiently managed, processed, and utilised across the system lifecycle.

III.2.4. Reference architecture framework description

The BlueBird project is designed with flexibility at its core, recognising that participants may have vastly different levels of existing IT infrastructure. To ensure broad applicability and ease of adoption, the system architecture supports a wide range of integration scenarios, from partial to full platform deployment, thereby facilitating seamless integration.

Participant Infrastructure Scenarios

- Participants with Existing IT Infrastructure:

Some participants may already possess their own IT infrastructure, including:

- Edge computing components such as IoT sensors, smart devices, and energy meters.
- A cloud computing platform equipped with foundational Big Data components, including:
 - A message broker (e.g., Apache Kafka or RabbitMQ)
 - A data lake for raw data storage
 - One or more lakeshores (i.e., structured and harmonised data repositories for analytics)

These participants may not require the complete BlueBird platform but may instead prefer to integrate specific BlueBird analytics services into their existing workflows selectively.

- Participants Without Existing Infrastructure:

Other participants might lack a complete IT setup or may only possess a subset of the necessary components. For these users, the BlueBird project provides a comprehensive platform that delivers all essential services, enabling full adoption of BlueBird's data processing and analytics capabilities without dependency on existing infrastructure.

- Pilot Sites and Technical Partners:

During testing and development phases, pilot sites or technical partners may need to deploy the BlueBird solution locally:

- On a development machine
- On-premises within a corporate network
- On a shared or private cloud platform

In all scenarios, the BlueBird platform is designed to be easily deployable and customisable, whether for experimentation, validation, or production use.

Minimum Requirements of the BlueBird Reference Architecture Framework

To maximise usability and interoperability, BlueBird services are designed to be integrated into existing IT structures. This integration is made possible by meeting a set of minimum architectural requirements, ensuring that the system is both robust and adaptable. To support a wide range of deployment and integration scenarios, the BlueBird reference architecture framework adheres to the following key requirements:

- Big Data Enabled: The architecture must comply with Big Data standards and support the core infrastructure required for large-scale data processing. This infrastructure includes:
 - A message broker for asynchronous, event-driven communication.
 - A data lake for centralised, unstructured data storage.

- At least one lakeshore, enabling structured and harmonised data representation suitable for analytics.
- Containerised Deployment: All BlueBird services are designed to be Docker-containerised, which ensures that they can be:
 - Easily installed and configured across diverse environments.
 - Portable, that could be deployed on local machines, on-premise infrastructure, or cloud platforms.
 - Managed and scaled using modern orchestration tools such as Docker Compose or Kubernetes.
- Modular and Composable Architecture: Following a microservices-based design, BlueBird services are:
 - Modular: Each service functions independently, allowing for easy updates or replacements of individual components without impacting the rest of the system.
 - Composable: Participants can customise or reconfigure the overall data flow and business logic by adjusting how services interact, primarily through changes in message broker topic configurations, allowing for flexible data pipelines and workflows.
 - This architectural flexibility empowers participants to either adopt BlueBird in whole or selectively integrate it into existing systems, depending on their specific operational needs and IT maturity. Whether used in development, pilot testing, or enterprise deployment, the BlueBird platform is designed to scale, adapt, and evolve in response to user requirements.

III.3. Reference architecture framework components explained

III.3.1. Ingestor Components

The Ingestor is a microservice that acts as the primary interface for receiving incoming data from external systems and field devices. It is responsible for capturing a wide variety of data types, such as raw sensor measurements, metadata, event logs, and system statuses, originating from IoT devices, field data loggers, or third-party services, and routing them into the internal system for processing.

Once received, the data is immediately forwarded to a designated message broker topic, typically referred to as the “input” topic, making it available for downstream services, such as the harmoniser.

The Ingestor is designed with the following operational characteristics to ensure reliability, scalability, and flexibility:

- Unsolicited Operation: The service operates in a listener mode, activating automatically in response to external transmissions without requiring polling or manual triggers.
- High Availability: It is built to maintain continuous operation with minimal downtime, ensuring uninterrupted data flow even under varying system loads.
- Responsiveness: It processes incoming data as promptly as possible, supporting real-time or near-real-time scenarios.
- Generic and Durable: The Ingestor is agnostic to data types, meaning it can handle different formats without needing to understand their structure or content. It supports the dynamic intake of new data types without requiring code changes or manual reconfiguration.
- Efficient Resource Usage: Designed to run with a minimal computational footprint, it efficiently utilises system resources even under high data volumes.

- **Scalability and Elasticity:** The service can be scaled horizontally, allowing multiple instances to run across distributed nodes. This characteristic enables increased throughput and flexible load distribution, with the ability to dynamically add, remove, or relocate instances as needed.
- **Robustness:** The Ingestor includes error-handling mechanisms that enable it to gracefully handle faulty or malformed inputs without compromising system stability.

The Ingestor serves as the entry point for data transmissions from field devices and external systems. Data are pushed to the “input” topic as soon as possible. From there, messages are ready to be consumed by the Harmoniser microservice. It is an HTTP-based ingestor that uses Spring Boot REST. The ingestor also uses Spring Kafka; all properties are configurable using the present Spring Kafka properties.

III.3.2. Harmonisation components

The Building Digital Twin is a comprehensive digital representation of a building’s physical and functional characteristics, relying on data aggregated from various heterogeneous sources. These include:

- Open data platforms (e.g., municipal energy datasets).
- Asset and facility management software (providing equipment specifications, schedules, and operational metadata).
- IoT devices and sensors (generating real-time measurements such as temperature, occupancy, or energy consumption).

Each of these sources utilises different data models and formats, posing a challenge for seamless integration and semantic interoperability. Commonly encountered data formats include:

- **Relational databases and XML:** Legacy formats are still widely in use in enterprise systems.
- **CSV (Comma-Separated Values):** A dominant format in Open Data portals and export tools for its simplicity.
- **JSON (JavaScript Object Notation):** Popular for its lightweight structure, particularly in web APIs and sensor communication.
- **RDF (Resource Description Framework):** Used as the federated, semantic data model that underpins cross-domain interoperability in the Digital Building Twin.

To address the challenge of harmonising such diverse data inputs, the harmoniser plays a critical role.

The harmoniser is a semantic transformation engine designed to convert heterogeneous energy-related building data into RDF format compliant with the ontology. Its primary objective is to ensure all relevant data, regardless of origin or format, can be integrated, queried, and understood uniformly within the system.

The harmoniser supports three primary data input sources:

- **JSON:** Often used for IoT and sensor data,
- **CSV:** Common in legacy systems and open government datasets,
- **RDF:** Already semantically enriched data requiring alignment with the ontology.

This component is built to comply with W3C standards for linked data and semantic web practices, ensuring interoperability with external systems and ontologies.

The harmoniser offers a modular set of features that systematically process and semantically enrich incoming data. These functionalities include:

- **JSON to RDF Transformation:** Converts raw JSON data into RDF triples that adhere to the ontology, ensuring that sensor and API-generated data are semantically structured and queryable.

- **CSV to RDF Transformation:** Processes structured CSV files, mapping rows and fields into RDF data conforming to the ontology. This process is commonly used for integrating data from open datasets and asset management exports.
- **Ontology Alignment with Existing Standards:** Aligns incoming RDF data with established semantic ontologies such as:
 - IFCOWL (building information modelling)
 - SAREF (smart appliances)
 - SSN/SOSA (sensors and observations)
 - geoNames, WGS84 (geolocation)
 - QUDT (quantities and units)
 - FOAF (agents and organisations)
- **Object-Class Mapping:** Provides tools to associate input data entities with appropriate classes in the ontology, ensuring each object is correctly typed in semantic terms.
- **Attribute-Property Mapping:** Allows mapping of incoming data attributes (such as temperature, power, or location) to the corresponding data properties in the ontology.
- **Inference of Implicit Relationships:** Detects and formalises implicit semantic links between data entities through object properties, enhancing the expressiveness and query capabilities of the dataset.
- **Value Reconciliation with External Registers:** Normalises and reconciles data values using official vocabularies, taxonomies, and controlled lists from:
 - Taxonomy enumerations
 - Open government registers
 - External domain-specific standards
- **Context Materialisation:** Enriches data with contextual metadata, such as temporal information, provenance, data source, or spatial boundaries, which are critical for accurate interpretation and analysis.

III.3.3. BlueBird components: Data processing and analysis components for BlueBird services

BlueBird components will be available in a component orchestration GUI (WP6-T6.4). This GUI will provide all the Dockerised components developed within the project, with the aim of deploying the BlueBird services across all the project's business cases.

Figure 9. BlueBird modules diagram

The project's technical partners will develop each component, and the technical partner assigned to each business case will deploy it at each pilot site. The Bluebird platform will have these general components, which will be deployed in the project pilots depending on the pilot's use case needs:

- **Forecast services (WP3 - T3.1):** To predict the behaviour of buildings and assets, forecasts of external conditions are needed. For this, the forecast services are expected to develop:
 - **Weather forecast models** that take Numerical Weather Predictions (NWP) as input and optimise them for local conditions using local observed data.
 - **Day-ahead forecast market prices** on bids and activation for short-term markets, in many situations using NWP as inputs.

Moreover, as data-driven Digital Twins are typically trained on the data sources that will underpin the simulations, a historical forecast dataset will be used to train models that utilise these forecast services.

- **Data-driven Digital Twin models (WP3 - T3.5):** data-driven models will be developed to create a Digital Twin of all the required buildings and assets in all business cases. As in the various business cases, there are several building typologies, different requirements, and different assets; therefore, the models will be tailored to the business case's needs. The Digital Twin will use historical data from the buildings and historical forecasts to be trained. The trained Digital Twin will be used on the Flexibility Manager.
- **Flexibility Manager (WP3 - T3.3):** a framework in which the Digital Twins, forecasts and gathered data are used to get the flexibility capacity. Inside this component is where all the data is transformed and prepared to determine the flexibility capacity. This flexibility capacity is calculated on the "Flexibility Manager optimisation", then, when market interaction is required, this capacity is proportioned to the Trading Manager, which, in case of cost variations (by Flexibility market

bidding), will re-optimize the building operation under the new conditions and send them again to the Trading Manager. When there is no direct market interaction, the operation optimization is sent to the building through the Building Data Exchange Connectors.

- **Flexibility Manager optimisation (WP3 - T3.4):** optimisation module inside the Flexibility Manager, which optimises the buildings/assets operations according to the optimisation function.
- **Trading Manager (WP5 - T5.3):** a service that collects the market flexibility pricing and, together with the buildings and assets flexibility capabilities (from Flexibility Manager), combines them and sends them to the electric market and the flexibility manager. If market prices change through bidding optimisation, these new conditions are sent back to the Flexibility Manager to get the updated flexibility capacity. Inside the Trading Manager, there is:
 - **Trading Manager bidding optimisation (WP3 - T3.2):** a framework in which, for each market and business case, the bidding price to sell the flexibility to the market is calculated.
 - **Trading Manager DSO communication module (WP5 - T5.1&T5.2):** The deployment of selected standardized solutions that will be made available to operators and aggregators in order to broaden opportunities for collaboration and integration within the energy system.
- **User interaction tools (Gamification engine, quizzes, user GUIs) (WP4 - T4.3):** to assess and strengthen user engagement with energy flexibility and demand response strategies, the project employs interactive tools and evaluation methods aimed at both education and business model design. This interaction with users will be based on the different optimisations from the Flexibility Manager. Inside the user interaction tools component, there is:
 - **Gamification:** central to this effort is the Demand Response Simulation Game, which manages energy use in a virtual building during simulated DR events. Users make decisions such as adjusting thermostats or shifting appliance use, with their actions recorded to assess effectiveness, energy savings, and satisfaction.
 - **Quizzes:** complementing this is the Flexibility Challenge Quiz, which tests participants' knowledge of DR concepts and energy-saving practices. The quiz also gathers demographic data to identify knowledge gaps across gender, minority, and energy-poor groups, helping ensure inclusivity in the design of future flexibility services.
- **Building Data Exchange Connectors (WP6 - T6.3):** this component enables the bi-directional exchange of data between buildings, the BlueBird platform, and the electrical grid. It handles both metadata on controllable assets and operational data for performance optimisation and grid flexibility. To achieve this, it gathers the optimal operation from the Flexibility Manager. It utilises the developed connectors and adapters to send this operation to BEMS and actuators for its execution.

IV. PROPOSED IMPLEMENTATIONS BY BUSINESS CASE

IV.1. BC1 – Karno Residential buildings with geothermal- and PV-based heat grid

The use cases developed in the Karno business case focus on providing user recommendations to empower users in knowledge-based energy consumption, with the aim of reducing their energy consumption cost. Moreover, the use cases include an analysis of the district heating network with the objective of quantifying excess capacity to study the possibility of expanding the district heating network to serve additional consumers.

For this, the expected components in this pilot are presented in the following figure:

Figure 10. Expected BlueBird modules deployed in BC1

In Karno, cloud data management is handled by Google Cloud. At present, some basic data analysis is done through Grafana, but no cloud-native analytics solutions have been implemented yet. They have already developed scripts to transfer data from ThingsBoard to BigQuery using Google Cloud Run, which are containerized with Docker on the Google Cloud Platform. However, the current cloud architecture is temporary and subject to change, Thingsboard may disappear from the pipeline. Since Docker is already in use, deploying the BlueBird components in the expected containerized form should not pose any issues.

Figure 11. BC1 actual IoT data flow diagram

IV.2. BC2 - PV self-consumption optimisation and occupant-driven flexibility of public buildings on the Iberian electricity trading markets

The use cases developed in the AMB business case focus on activating public buildings with two control strategies. The first one involves controlling building assets by considering the time-of-use tariff (within day-ahead and intraday markets) and onsite-generated energy to reduce energy costs using the building's or service's flexibility. The second strategy is to determine the building's or asset's flexibility capabilities and sell them to the flexibility market through the aggregation of multiple similar building flexibilities.

For this, the expected components in this pilot are presented in the following figure. For the first control strategy, the Trading Manager will not be used, as there is no interaction with the flexibility trading market. Within the second control strategy, all components will be used, as there is interaction with the flexibility market, and when there is no agreement on selling the flexibility, the building assets will be optimised by pricing.

Figure 12. Expected BlueBird modules deployed in BC2

The BlueBird services in the AMB pilot are carried out by CIMNE. The IoT architecture is based on a Kubernetes micro service architecture. In this architecture there is an ingestor module prepared to receive data from APIs, MQTT, Bacnet and is prepared to be adaptable to new protocols if needed. The data received is managed differently if it's static data or time series data. If the received data is static is

harmonised and stored in a Neo4j non-structured database. If the data received is from a time series, is stored into HBASE in raw and is also harmonised and stored into InfluxDB database. In both cases, the harmonisation process consists on identifying the received data into the project data model and transform it to the project standard storage format. The architecture is deployed through Docker, therefore the BlueBird components deployment in the expected containerized form should not pose any issues.

Figure 13. BC1 actual IoT data flow diagram

IV.3. BC3 – Tour & Taxis site: Mixed-use buildings and REN

The use cases developed in the Wesmart business case focus on providing user recommendations to empower users in knowledge-based energy consumption, with the aim of reducing their energy consumption cost. For these recommendations is needed some knowledge from the electric market which will be provided through the Trading Manager.

For this, the expected components in this pilot are presented in the following figure:

Figure 14. Expected BlueBird modules deployed in BC3

The architecture deployed on the BC3 is based on a central PostgreSQL with an interface through API to communicate with. Then they have a visualisation module based on React (JavaScript) which communicates with the data base in the backend to provide the required data to the visualisation panels for user consultation. The actual architecture is based on Dockers, therefore the BlueBird components deployment in the expected containerized form should not pose any issues.

IV.4. BC4 - ENEA Operator – Office Building

The use cases developed in the 4th business case focus on actuating the ENEA Operator office building with two control strategies. On one side, it will actively actuate through the thermostats to reduce heating costs. On the other side, it will be actuated through user behaviour interaction with the same objective of assessing which benefits can be reached using both strategies.

For this, the expected components in this pilot are presented in the following figure:

Figure 15. Expected BlueBird modules deployed in BC4

The IoT architecture is being provided by PSNC, and its definition is still under development. It is expected to run in a Docker environment, likely deployed on Ubuntu. The message broker will be based on MQTT, directing data to two different databases: one for static data and another for time-series data. The time-series database will likely be PostgreSQL. In this business case, the overall architecture will already be deployed through Docker, so the BlueBird components should be containerised without issue. However, since the buildings in this pilot are part of Poland’s electric grid, a critical national infrastructure, the deployed services must first be delivered as code for security validation before being Dockerised.

IV.5. BC5 - PSNC & ENEA Operator – Grid Building

The use cases developed in the PSNC and ENEA Operator business case focus on activating a grid building to test the interaction with the market, with a theoretical control expansion involving multiple grid buildings. Within the test control strategy, the flexibility capacity will be offered to the flexibility market. If an agreement is reached, the activation behaviour will be set following the agreed-upon terms with the market operator. In the event of no agreement on selling the flexibility, the building assets will be optimised by operational costs.

For this, the expected components in this pilot are presented in the following figure:

Figure 16. Expected BlueBird modules deployed in BC5

The IoT architecture is being provided by PSNC, and its definition is still under development. It is expected to run in a Docker environment, likely deployed on Ubuntu. The message broker will be based on MQTT, directing data to two different databases: one for static data and another for time-series data. The time-series database will likely be PostgreSQL. In this business case, the overall architecture will already be deployed through Docker, so the BlueBird components should be containerised without issue. However, since the buildings in this pilot are part of Poland's electric grid, a critical national infrastructure, the deployed services must first be delivered as code for security validation before being Dockerised.

IV.6. BC6 – ENK Waterworks building with renewable storage

The use cases developed in the ENLION business case focus on activating the waterworks with two control strategies. The first one involves controlling the waterworks, considering energy pricing and onsite-generated energy to reduce energy costs using the waterworks’ facilities’ energy flexibility. The second strategy is to determine the waterworks’ flexibility capabilities and sell them to the flexibility market through the aggregation of multiple building flexibilities.

For this, the expected components in this pilot are presented in the following figure. For the first control strategy, the Trading Manager will not be used, as there is no interaction with the flexibility trading market. Within the second control strategy, all components will be used, as there is interaction with the flexibility market, and when there is no agreement on selling the flexibility, the building assets will be optimised by pricing.

Figure 17. Expected BlueBird modules deployed in BC6

The BlueBird services deployed in the ENLION business case are provided directly by ENLION. Their current IT architecture consists of a Kafka cluster connected via MQTT, with InfluxDB as the primary database. The existing Virtual Power Plant (VPP) is based on Siemens’ proprietary automation software, running within a Docker environment. All BlueBird services will be deployed on a cloud server running Ubuntu 24.04 (or a similar version). Since ENLION already works with Docker and Ubuntu provides full support for containerization, deploying the BlueBird components in the expected containerised form should not present any difficulties.

Architecture

Figure 18. BC6 actual IoT data flow diagram

IV.7. BC7 – Hotels with PV, biomass-driven CHP and charging stations

The use cases developed in the EWH business case have several primary objectives for deployment in hotel facilities. One objective is to control and regulate the temperature in the hotel cool rooms with the aim of reducing energy costs, taking into account electricity pricing. The other objective is linked to the use of EV chargers. On one side, it aims to interact with users to minimise electricity costs. On the other hand, it aims to control the output power from EV chargers to test the option of selling flexibility to the market and assess its economic benefits.

For this, the expected components in this pilot are presented in the following figure:

Figure 19. Expected BlueBird modules deployed in BC7

The BlueBird services deployed in BC7 are going to be hosted by ENLION. Their current IT architecture includes a Kafka cluster connected via MQTT, with InfluxDB serving as the primary database. The existing Virtual Power Plant (VPP) relies on Siemens’ proprietary automation software, operating within a Docker environment. All BlueBird services will be deployed on a cloud server running Ubuntu 24.04 (or a similar version). Since ENLION already uses Docker and Ubuntu offers full support for containerization, deploying the BlueBird components in the expected containerised form should not present any difficulties. On the EWH side, measurement data will be provided to the ENLION platform through the architecture’s MQTT.

Architecture

Figure 20. BC7 expected IoT data flow diagram

V. CONCLUSION

A comprehensive general architecture has been designed to integrate seamlessly with existing IoT infrastructures in pilot sites, while also ensuring that the minimum requirements are met for deploying the full suite of BlueBird services. This architecture strikes a balance between flexibility and robustness, providing a versatile foundation for energy data management and demand response applications.

The deliverable outlines the minimum architectural requirements in various deployment scenarios, providing IT deployers with multiple options to host and operate BlueBird services using containerised solutions. This adaptability ensures that the architecture can be efficiently applied across diverse environments, from local premises to cloud-based infrastructures.

Through the careful design of its components and tools, spanning data ingestion, harmonisation, user engagement mechanisms, and system integration, the BlueBird architecture enables a truly holistic approach to energy management. Specifically, the architecture ensures:

1. Robust Data Ingestion and Exposure by enabling reliable capture and sharing of information from sensors, devices, and building systems.
2. Semantic Harmonisation for Interoperability by ensuring that heterogeneous data is transformed into a consistent, semantically enriched format aligned with established ontologies.
3. Easy deployment in most environments due to the use of Docker containers to deploy the BlueBird Services.
4. Integration with Energy Systems and the Grid by supporting bi-directional communication between building energy assets, the BlueBird platform, and the wider electrical grid for optimisation and flexibility services.

The IT infrastructure intended for the deployment of all BlueBird services in all the pilots has been thoroughly analysed, and no major barriers have been identified that could hinder the deployment of these services.

